

THE VALUE OF QUALITY OF LIFE AS AN INDICATOR FOR ASSESSING THE COURSE OF ENDOMETRIOSIS

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Summary: Despite the huge achievements in the study of the period of perimenopause, this problem continues to attract the attention of both scientists and practitioners, as is the problem of managing patients with endometrioid disease.

The quality of life of patients with endometrioid disease in the period of perimenopause is significantly affected. Frequent changes in mood, depression, and anxiety often interfere with everyday work, despite the fact that the components of physical health remain at an average level.

Key words: increase, the main group, depression, significantly affected.

Relevance. Despite the huge achievements in the study of the period of perimenopause, this problem continues to attract the attention of both scientists and practitioners, as is the problem of managing patients with endometrioid disease.

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An increase in the number of women with endometriosis suffering from menopausal syndrome requires the development of a new approach to the treatment of this category of women and is one of the urgent problems of modern gynecology, which served as the basis for our study.

Purpose of the study. To study the clinical course of menopausal syndrome in women with endometriosis based on the study of quality of life, hormonal status and treatment methods used.

Material and method research. We examined 142 women in the period of perimenopause with endometriosis from the age of 45 to 55 years, who contacted a gynecologist about complaints related to the manifestations of menopausal syndrome. A survey was conducted on the questionnaire of quality of life

Patients were divided into 2 groups: group I consisted of 40 women (operated on for endometriosis), group II consisted of 47 women (not operated on for endometriosis). The control group consisted of 50 women aged 45-55 years without gynecological pathology.

The results of the study. A weak severity of menopausal syndrome according to the Kupperman index was noted in the main group -20.3% of patients, medium-66% and severe-32%. In the control group, the severity of menopausal syndrome according to the Kupperman index: a weak degree in 18, an average degree in 14%, severe in 5%.

Correction of psychoemotional and vegetovascular disorders was carried out with the drug Proslupine (active substance, sulpiride) 200 mg, the drug was prescribed 2 times a day, 100 mg until 4 p.m. Control was carried out after 1, 3, 6 weeks.

According to the quality of life questionnaire -SF36, in women with endometriosis during the period of perimenopause before treatment, a decrease in the quality of life was noted, in the main group - 56%, in the control group - 72%.

After the treatment, a significant improvement in the psychoemotional state and an increase in the quality of life of patients were noted both in the main group 89% and in the control -96%.

Findings. Thus, the literature review and our own research indicate the feasibility of treating patients with endometriosis during the perimenopause period with psychoemotional and vegetative vascular disorders with atypical small antipsychotic drugs, which allows to increase the clinical effectiveness of complex treatment and improve the quality of life of perimenopausal women.

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